

Village Fund Direct Cash Assistance and Its Role in Poverty Reduction: An Empirical Analysis from Indonesia

Muhammad Ronal Istanto Ismail¹, Irawati Igrisa², Sri Yulianty Mozin³

¹Student of Master of Public Administration Program, Gorontalo State University, Gorontalo, Indonesia

^{2,3}Lecturer of Master of Public Administration Program, Gorontalo State University, Gorontalo, Indonesia

ABSTRACT: The study aims to find out and describe the effectiveness of the Village Fund Direct Cash Assistance program for the poor in Dungaliyo District. The research approach used is a qualitative method with a descriptive research method and a research procedure carried out by observation and interviews with informants. The data analysis technique used is an interactive analysis of the Miles and Huberman model. The results of the study show that the Village Fund Direct Cash Assistance Program (BLTDD) for the poor in Dungaliyo District, Gorontalo Regency has made a positive contribution in improving the welfare of people in need. The program has generally been running well although there is room for improvement, especially in target accuracy, socialization, and monitoring. A more holistic approach to implementation and evaluation can increase the effectiveness of the program, resulting in a more equitable and sustainable positive impact on the poor. The results of each sub-focus are: (1) the accuracy of the targets of the BLT Village Fund program in Dungaliyo District has been quite good with the efforts to improve recipient data carried out by the village government. While there are still challenges in reaching all poor families equally, the steps taken demonstrate a commitment to ensuring that assistance is received by those who really need it. (2) the socialization of the BLT Village Fund program in Dungaliyo District has been carried out through various information channels, including the village government and related officials. However, the implementation needs to be more intensive so that the public better understands the objectives, benefits, and mechanisms of the program. (3) the main purpose of the BLT Dana Desa program is to help poor families meet their basic needs and support the economic recovery of the village. In Dungaliyo District, this program has been quite effective in reducing the economic burden of the poor. (4) monitoring of the implementation of the Village Fund BLT program in Dungaliyo District has been carried out routinely by the village government and related parties. This effort is quite effective in ensuring that assistance is received by those who are eligible.

KEYWORDS: Community, Direct Cash Assistance, Dungaliyo, Poor, Program.

INTRODUCTION

Villages are the object of development. This is evidenced by the budget allocation through the Village Fund so as to accelerate development acceleration in Indonesia. Village Law number 6 of 2014 is a form of the Government's commitment to provide opportunities for villages to carry out control planning as well as evaluation in terms of determining the direction of policies which ultimately are the welfare of the community in accordance with the conditions of the village. (Bender, 2014). The concept of building from the village is not only supported by the delegation of authority by the government to the regions but also adequate budget support through the State expenditure budget to the Regional Government, to budget support to the Village level through the Village Fund Budget. Budget support through the Village Fund is expected to increase the acceleration of development so that the concept of building from the village is not only a slogan and tagline of the government but is actually implemented and becomes an indicator in supporting and implementing national development targets in accordance with the RPJMN.

The Village Regulation and Village Fund policies are regulated in (1) Law No. 6 of 2014 concerning Villages; (2) Government Regulation No. 47 of 2015 concerning Amendments to Government Regulation No. 43 of 2014 concerning Regulations for the Implementation of Law No. 6 of 2014; and (3) Government Regulation No. 8 of 2016 concerning the Second Amendment to Government Regulation No. 60 of 2014 concerning Village Funds sourced from the State Budget.

Direct cash assistance for village funds (BLT-DD) itself is regulated in the National Priority Program of village authority to support the elimination of extreme poverty. As stipulated in Permendes No. 8 of 2022, in the context of alleviating extreme poverty, the direct cash assistance program is still a solution so that in 2023. The Village Government is expected to allocate Village Funds to

help people who are still affected by extreme poverty (Permendes PDTT, 2022). The amount of BLT-DD allocation from the Village Fund budget is a maximum of 25% of the Village Fund Ceiling and a minimum of 10%. (article updesa.com) while the management of village funds in 2023 is regulated in the Minister of Finance Regulation number 201/PMK.07/2022.

Based on initial observations in the field, there are several factors that affect the effectiveness of cash assistance in the distribution of Village Funds in Dungaliyo District. First, obstacles in the accuracy of targets. Even though they have operational criteria and standards, not all village communities that meet the criteria receive direct assistance. On the other hand, there are also people who are not eligible but receive assistance. Obstacles in program socialization. Many village people still do not know about this BLT-DD program. Socialization is important to increase information transparency about BLT-DD. The government needs to strengthen cross-work and communication systems to provide the latest information to the public and solve problems in the distribution of BLT-DD. Obstacles in program objectives. The BLT-DD program is aimed at improving the welfare of village communities, but in some cases only creates a short-term distribution of aid. One of the main obstacles in achieving this goal is the incomplete implementation. Many regions have become critical of the provisions of BLT-DD which are designed without considering geographical conditions and the ability of local human resources. Instead, a more important element in achieving program success is collaborative thinking. The existence of community participation in this program will strengthen and ensure the success of the program in the future.

Obstacles in program monitoring. Although the BLT-DD program has been launched, there is no guarantee that it will be implemented effectively. Good supervision will ensure that the BLT-DD program runs with and provides benefits for the village community. Program monitoring is important to assess the effectiveness of the BLT-DD program. The implementation of monitoring requires a trained and skilled team, which is still supported by adequate infrastructure information. The government must ensure that such a monitoring system is efficient, effective, and able to evaluate the success of the BLT-DD that is launched. By making initial observations of the amount of Village Funds allocated for Direct Cash Assistance and the families of beneficiaries of assistance to the community. In addition to observing the amount of Village funds, the author also collected initial data on the recipients of assistance based on the poor from the Gorontalo Regency Social Service and juxtaposed with DTKS data which is one of the indicators for determining prospective recipients of direct cash assistance.

The BLT-DD program is very important for the welfare of the village community. There is a need to increase effectiveness in the aspects of target accuracy, program socialization, program objectives and program monitoring by maintaining appropriate and continuous verification in seeking qualifications for distributing aid appropriately, strengthening program socialization, developing a more long-term program scheme, and strengthening program monitoring and evaluation. By increasing the effectiveness of this program, the BLT-DD program can help reduce poverty problems and provide long-term benefits for the future of village communities in Dungaliyo District.

METHOD

The place and location of the research are in Dungaliyo District, Gorontalo Regency. The time for this research is planned to be carried out for 6 months from the preparation of proposals, tabulation, analysis and interpretation of data to the preparation of research results. The research approach used is a qualitative method with a descriptive research method and a research procedure carried out by observation and interviews with informants. The data analysis technique used is an interactive analysis of the miles and huberman model.

RESEARCH RESULTS

A. Description of Research Results

1. Presentation of the accuracy of the target of the village fund direct cash assistance program for the poor in villages in Dungaliyo District, Gorontalo Regency

a. Criteria for receiving BLT Village Funds

The accuracy of the target of aid recipients is an aspect that has been sought through a systematic selection process and involving various parties. The village government, through village deliberations (Musdes), plays an important role in determining the criteria and list of recipients based on the most urgent needs. These criteria include the poor, those who do not have a fixed income, and other criteria according to government regulations. This process aims to ensure that assistance is on target and received by people

who really need it. The Village Fund BLT program in Dungaliyo District has been designed and implemented by paying attention to the accuracy of targets based on relevant criteria.

b. Obstacles and data collection of BLT recipients of Village Funds

The implementation of this program is mostly going well, although there are some technical challenges. Data collection and distribution of BLT are carried out through a village deliberation mechanism (Musdes) involving the village head, the Village Consultative Body (BPD), village government officials, and the community. This process shows solid coordination and cooperation in determining the right beneficiaries. Although the implementation of the BLT Dana Desa program is not completely free from obstacles, the mechanism for data collection, selection, and distribution of aid has been well designed to minimize obstacles. Village and district governments show a high commitment to ensuring that assistance is on target and received by people in need. On the other hand, the appreciation from the beneficiary community is an indicator that this program has a positive impact on the welfare of the community in villages in Dungaliyo District.

c. Accuracy of the target recipients of BLT Village Funds

This program has been sought to reach the poor who are most in need. However, there are still challenges in ensuring that all recipients of assistance are truly in accordance with the criteria set, especially in areas with high levels of extreme poverty. People who are really experiencing economic difficulties are the top priority in determining aid recipients. The village government continues to be encouraged to re-collect data in more detail so that no community is missed, especially those in hard-to-reach geographical locations. Even though the BLT Village Fund program has been running according to the existing mechanism, there is still room for improvement. A more inclusive approach is needed to ensure that no community in real need of assistance is missed in the data collection and distribution process. Increased coordination between village governments, BPDs, and communities is essential to identify the most vulnerable community groups.

d. Periodic evaluation of data on BLT recipients of Village Funds

An evaluation process has been made to ensure the accuracy of the program's objectives. This evaluation is carried out through various mechanisms involving the participation of the village government, the Village Consultative Body (BPD), as well as key figures such as the head of the hamlet who has in-depth knowledge of the condition of the community in his area. These changes usually include certain cases, such as recipients who have died, moved their place of residence, or no longer meet the criteria set. Hamlet heads play an important role in recording their citizens, because they are the ones who know the real condition of the community the most. This approach reflects the existence of a community-based monitoring system to maintain the accuracy of recipient data.

e. Potential inaccuracies in recipients of BLT Village Funds

The data on BLT Village Fund recipients is in accordance with the criteria and results of village deliberations. In fact, they admit that there are still people in need but have not been covered by assistance, considering the limited quota and allocation of available funds. This shows that, although data collection has been considered adequate, there are structural limitations that make all communities that meet the criteria unreachable. So even though efforts to collect data and distribute aid have been carefully carried out by the village, there are still several obstacles related to the accuracy of the target. The accuracy of the Village Fund BLT target is a challenge that requires constant attention. Factors such as limited quotas, lack of accuracy in data collection, and verification mechanisms that are not fully optimal are the main causes of potential inaccuracies in recipients. Although village and district governments have made efforts to minimize errors, openness in the data collection process and more intensive supervision are still needed.

2. Presentation of the socialization of the village fund direct cash assistance program for the poor in villages in Dungaliyo District, Gorontalo Regency

a. Socialization of the BLT Village Fund program

Efforts to disseminate information about this program have been carried out through various communication channels. The socialization of this program aims to ensure that the community, especially the target groups, get accurate and timely information about the technical implementation, recipient criteria, and aid distribution schedules. The majority of people receive information through the head of the hamlet or the local RT. However, there are still cases where information is uneven, so people have to share

information with each other informally. This obstacle indicates that even though the information delivery system has been designed in such a way, there are still gaps in the distribution of information that need to be improved so that all people have equal access to information. The socialization of the BLT Village Fund program in Dungaliyo District has been carried out through various approaches. However, there are challenges in the form of gaps in access to information, especially in remote areas or for people who are not active in village forums.

b. Clarity of information in the socialization of the BLT Village Fund program

Socialization efforts have been carried out by the village and sub-district governments through various channels, but there are several obstacles in conveying clear and consistent information to the community. The socialization carried out has two levels, namely at the village level which is more direct and touches the needs of the community, and at the sub-district level which tends to be general. The socialization carried out by village officials is considered to have included community meetings and direct information delivery. However, the district government also underlined the importance of providing a more detailed explanation regarding the criteria for beneficiaries and procedures for disbursing assistance, especially for people who have just been included in the list of BLT recipients of village funds in Dungaliyo District. Although the socialization of the BLT Dana Desa program has been carried out through direct meetings and other communication channels, there is still room for improvement, especially in ensuring the clarity and consistency of the information conveyed.

c. Socialization method of the BLT Village Fund program

The socialization method used needs to be perfected so that the information conveyed is clearer and easier to understand by all levels of society. People who do not understand the complaint mechanism well tend to feel confused when facing problems related to the assistance received. The methods used in program socialization need to focus more on providing comprehensive and practical information, including ways to access complaint services. In addition, it is important for the village government to provide a more detailed explanation of the beneficiaries' rights and responsibilities, so that there is no confusion or misunderstanding in the future. Village governments are advised to pay more attention to the method of delivering information, in a more direct and accessible way for residents, including those who live in areas with limited access to information.

d. Evaluation of the effectiveness of the socialization of the BLT Village Fund program

People have begun to understand their right to receive assistance as well as their obligation to provide accurate information regarding their condition. The village government reported that after the socialization, the community's awareness of their rights increased, including an understanding of their obligation to report changes in conditions. Although the socialization has been carried out well, there are still several aspects that need to be improved to improve understanding and more effective program implementation. Although the effectiveness of the socialization of the BLT Dana Desa program in Dungaliyo District can be said to be quite good, there are several aspects that need to be improved. One of them is the importance of clarifying the reporting mechanism in the event of a problem or change in conditions.

e. The involvement of the parties in the socialization of the BLT Dana Desa program

The implementation of socialization has gone well, but there are several areas that still need improvement to better involve the community and facilitate access to information. The community will be more actively involved if they are given the space to ask questions and discuss directly about the program. Socialization that is more two-way will provide opportunities for the public to understand better, and can reduce their confusion about the BLT program. Therefore, small group discussions are considered an effective way to ensure that communities truly understand every important aspect of the assistance received, including their rights and obligations as beneficiaries. So that the BLT Village Fund socialization program has been implemented well, although there are several things that need to be improved to better involve the community.

3. Presentation of the purpose of the village fund direct cash assistance program for the poor in villages in Dungaliyo District, Gorontalo Regency

a. The main objectives of the implementation of the BLT Village Fund program

The program's objectives are collectively geared towards providing direct financial support to the poor, with a primary focus on meeting urgent basic needs. The purpose of the BLT Dana Desa program is to ensure that the assistance provided can be used to meet the mandatory needs of beneficiaries. The program is considered one way to support those who really need help, with the

money received directly allocated to urgent primary needs. This shows that the BLT Dana Desa program not only provides cash assistance in general, but is also directed to reduce the difficulties of the poor in meeting their daily basic needs. The main purpose of the BLT Dana Desa program is to provide direct assistance that can be used to meet the basic needs of beneficiaries, such as food and education.

b. The success of the implementation of the Village Fund BLT program

The program has had a significant positive impact, but its success has been temporary and has limitations in covering all the needs of the poor. Although the BLT Dana Desa program is quite effective in helping to meet the basic needs of the community, such as food, there are some conditions that cannot be fully overcome by this assistance, especially more specific and in-depth needs, such as medical expenses. Beneficiaries, especially the elderly who often suffer from illnesses, feel that the assistance provided is only sufficient for basic needs such as food, but not enough to pay for the treatment they need. This shows that although this cash assistance provides assistance to several sectors of life, there are still other important aspects that need to be considered for the success of this program to be more comprehensive.

c. Tujuan program BLT Dana Desa dalam reduksi kemiskinan

The program aims to help the poor, but its success still depends on other factors, including the availability of funds and more sustainable economic empowerment efforts. The amount of assistance provided is still limited and not always sufficient, especially for more vulnerable groups, such as the elderly who do not have a family or other source of income. The village government hopes that with an increase in the allocation of funds from the central government, the amount of assistance can be increased so that it is better able to reach all levels of society in need.

d. Follow-up to the objectives of the BLT Village Fund program

The village fund BLT program has been in accordance with the urgent needs of the poor, there is a strong awareness from various parties regarding the importance of continuation and adjustment of the program to be more effective and sustainable. Although BLT helps in meeting the basic needs of the community, to achieve a more sustainable improvement in welfare, the community needs broader support, such as providing assistance that can encourage them to entrepreneurship or develop the potential of the local economy. This kind of assistance, according to the village government, can accelerate the economic recovery of the community, especially those who depend on informal economic sectors. The follow-up to the BLT Village Fund program must include increasing the diversity of types of assistance, such as food assistance or MSME support, as well as adjusting the value of assistance based on more flexible local conditions.

e. Follow-up to the objectives of the BLT Village Fund program

The village fund BLT program has provided benefits to the poor, there is awareness from various parties that to ensure the sustainability and effectiveness of the program, further adjustments and development are needed. The distribution of aid must be based on a clear analysis of what are the basic needs of the community. In other words, it is important to do mapping in advance so that the assistance provided is right on target. This adjustment aims to ensure that the recipients of assistance are those who really need it, and in accordance with the criteria that have been set. This shows that there are efforts to ensure that the BLT program is really effective in providing support to the poor, as well as avoiding untargeted distribution.

4. Exposure to monitoring the direct cash assistance program for village funds for the poor in villages in Dungaliyo District, Gorontalo Regency

a. Monitoring the distribution of BLT Village Funds

There are collaborative efforts in supervision and monitoring, but there is still a need for improvement in the mechanism for collecting input from beneficiaries (KPM). There needs to be a more formal mechanism to collect input from beneficiaries. This shows the awareness of the importance of transparency and community participation in supervision, as well as the need for a more systematic system to capture the aspirations of recipients. Although LPM is already involved in supervision, they feel that the methods used today are less efficient in accommodating direct feedback from the community.

b. Responsibility for monitoring and reporting the distribution of BLT Village Funds

There is a clear mechanism for reporting and monitoring, which of course cannot be separated from various challenges related to the speed of response and simplicity of the reporting process. Reports on the distribution of Village Fund BLT are usually submitted to the village government. This reporting process is considered quite easy, but there are obstacles to response that sometimes take time. This reflects that while there are reporting channels available, the follow-up process on the report is not yet fully efficient. A late response can hinder efforts to monitor and evaluate the program, thus impacting the quality and transparency of the distribution of BLT assistance for village funds.

c. Reporting mechanism for BLT Village Fund obstacles

There was a good and fast response from the village government, but with bureaucratic and technical constraints it still affected the smooth resolution of the problem. In general, the response to problem reports is quite good, but often the solution to the problem is constrained by the existing bureaucracy. Bureaucracy, although sometimes an obstacle, can also play a role in supporting problem solving if the mechanism is working well. This reflects the gap between formal administrative processes and the urgent need to resolve issues immediately, which can slow down the handling of complaints or errors that occur in the distribution of aid.

d. Periodic evaluation of the use of BLT Village Fund funds

There are quite systematic efforts in program monitoring, but it also reflects several challenges related to transparency and communication regarding the evaluation process. Program monitoring is carried out by the village government, BPD (Village Consultative Body), and LPM (Community Empowerment Institution). However, they acknowledged that the evaluation process needs to be more transparent so that all parties, both beneficiaries and supervisory agencies, can understand more clearly how BLT funds are used and who is involved in the evaluation. This lack of transparency, if not corrected, can reduce public confidence in the implementation of the program, especially related to the distribution of funds and the achievement of program goals.

a. Follow-up efforts and complaints of BLT Village Funds

There are a number of steps that are considered important to increase the success and effectiveness of the program. The three main issues raised by the informant are improved beneficiary data, increased transparency, and stricter supervision. Improving beneficiary data is an important step that needs to be taken to ensure that the BLT program runs well. They also emphasized the importance of more intensive socialization to the community, so that all parties clearly understand the beneficiary criteria and implementation procedures. In addition, stricter supervision by village officials and related institutions is expected to prevent misuse of funds or injustice in the distribution of aid. This reflects that the village government realizes the importance of a transparent and controlled mechanism to ensure the effectiveness of the program.

5. Findings of the Research Results

The problem of poverty is a problem that is still faced in Indonesia. There are three views on poverty, namely: (1) poverty means insufficient income to meet the most basic needs to maintain the continuity of life. (2) Low income must be measured subjectively, which is relatively low relative to the income of others in society. (3) poverty is linked to a person's efforts to obtain adequate income. Poverty determines the level of development of a society and is one of the indicators of the unsuccessful development process. The problem of poverty continues to be a problem for people and countries in this world from time to time. Various efforts have been made to reduce poverty. Efforts to reduce poverty are actually not only the responsibility of the government, but also the responsibility of the community itself. The government also continues to strive to reduce poverty rates with poverty alleviation programs in various sectors of life

Direct Cash Assistance (BLT) is a form of social intervention designed to provide direct financial assistance to poor families or individuals affected by difficult economic conditions. The relationship between BLT and poverty reduction is very close because this program can help reduce the economic burden of the poor in the short term. By receiving BLT, poor families get additional income that can be used to meet basic needs such as food, health, education, and other needs that are often difficult to reach for those in limited economic conditions.

The accuracy of the targets in the Village Fund Direct Cash Assistance (BLT) program in Dungaliyo District, Gorontalo Regency has significant challenges. Based on the findings of the study, although the village government tries hard to record and ensure the right beneficiaries, there are still a number of obstacles that cause some families not to be registered or not to receive assistance

even though they are classified as poor. One of the main factors is the inconsistency of data owned by the village government with real conditions in the field. Data collection processes that are not completely accurate often result in errors in the selection of aid recipients. For this reason, improvements are needed in the data collection and verification system that is more thorough so that assistance can be on target, considering that the main goal of this program is to help people who really need it.

The socialization of the Village Fund Direct Cash Assistance (BLT) program in Dungaliyo District, Gorontalo Regency, although carried out periodically by the village government, still has several shortcomings that affect the community's understanding of the program. Based on the results of the research, the socialization carried out relies more on conventional methods such as public meetings and village deliberations, but has not been fully effective in reaching all levels of society, especially those in remote areas or less exposed to information. Some beneficiaries feel that they have not been given enough understanding of the registration procedure, recipient criteria, and benefits from the assistance. Therefore, innovations are needed in socialization methods, such as utilizing social media or conducting direct counseling to residents' homes so that information about this program can be more evenly distributed and well understood by the entire community.

The main objective of the Village Fund Direct Cash Assistance (BLT) program in Dungaliyo District is to provide direct support to poor families to improve their welfare, especially in facing economic difficulties caused by various factors. Based on the results of the research, this program aims to reduce the economic burden of rural communities affected by poverty, so that they can meet basic needs such as food, education, and health. In addition, the BLT program is also expected to accelerate the process of empowering village communities by providing better access to social assistance from the government. However, there are concerns that many communities are not fully benefiting from the program due to inaccuracy of the targets or lack of understanding of how to take advantage of the assistance provided.

Monitoring of the Village Fund Direct Cash Assistance (BLT) program in Dungaliyo District is carried out regularly by the village government, but the results of the study show that the existing monitoring mechanism still needs improvement. The village government, together with the Village Consultative Body (BPD) and the Community Empowerment Institute (LPM), evaluated the distribution of BLT, but limitations in transparency and communication were the main obstacles. Many residents feel that they are not directly involved in the monitoring process, so they only know the final results of the monitoring without knowing the details of the process. Therefore, a more transparent and participatory monitoring system is needed, involving the community directly so that they can be more active in providing feedback on the distribution of aid and the implementation of this program.

BLT also functions as a lever in improving social welfare by providing a sense of financial security, especially in times of crisis or disaster. This assistance can keep poor families from falling further into extreme poverty. In the long term, although BLT is not a permanent solution to overcome poverty, this program contributes to poverty reduction by preventing the survival of the poor from weakening. As part of the social policy strategy, BLT has a positive impact on people's purchasing power, which in turn can stimulate the local economy and help in the economic recovery process of people affected by the crisis.

Meanwhile, the findings regarding the BLT ceiling of village funds in Dungaliyo District, Gorontalo Regency are presented as follows:

Figure 4.1: Village Fund Ceiling in Dungaliyo District

Based on the graph above, it can be seen that the budget for Direct Cash Assistance for Village Funds (BLTDD) in Dungaliyo District, Gorontalo Regency, can be concluded that there is a significant variation in the allocation of funds received by each village. Ambara Village received the largest budget allocation of Rp 1,022,210,000, which shows that this village has a larger number of aid recipients or greater budget needs for the poor. In contrast, some villages such as Duwanga and Bongomeme have smaller allocations, amounting to Rp 72,000,000 and Rp 86,400,000, respectively, which could reflect a smaller number of recipients or assistance needs.

This variation in budget allocation reflects the difference in the level of socio-economic needs of the community in each village. Some villages with large budgets such as Ambara and Pilolalenga have a larger number of beneficiary families (KPM) or higher poverty rates. Meanwhile, villages with smaller budgets face a limited number of recipients or have more efficient budgets in distribution. However, overall, the BLTDD program in these villages is expected to have a positive impact on the welfare of the poor by paying attention to the appropriate allocation and in accordance with local needs. This program aims to improve the economic welfare of village communities in need by providing direct cash assistance from village funds.

A. Discussion

The results of the analysis found that the Village Fund Direct Cash Assistance (BLTDD) program for the poor in Dungaliyo District is quite effective in providing direct assistance to poor families to meet the basic needs of the community. However, there are challenges in terms of target accuracy, limited socialization, and monitoring that is not fully optimal. However, with efforts to improve the data collection system, increase more inclusive socialization, and stricter monitoring, the BLT village fund program has the potential to have a greater positive impact on the welfare of the poor in the villages of Dungaliyo District, Gorontalo Regency. The results of each sub-focus regarding the effectiveness of the village fund direct cash assistance program for the poor in villages in Dungaliyo District, Gorontalo Regency are described as follows:

1. Accuracy of the target of the village fund direct cash assistance program for the poor in villages in Dungaliyo District, Gorontalo Regency

The accuracy of the target in the Village Fund Direct Cash Assistance (BLT) program for the poor in villages in Dungaliyo District, Gorontalo Regency refers to the ability of the village government to distribute assistance to individuals or families who really meet the criteria as beneficiaries. In this context, the accuracy of the target includes an accurate and transparent data collection process, so that assistance can be received by those who need it most, namely residents living in extreme poverty. The recipient selection process must be based on valid data and involve community participation to avoid errors or data manipulation. By ensuring the accuracy of the targets, this program can have a greater impact on poverty alleviation

The accuracy of the targets of the Village Fund Direct Cash Assistance (BLTDD) program is very important to ensure that the assistance distributed is appropriate for groups in need. In villages in Dungaliyo District, there is a challenge in ensuring that only the poor are beneficiaries. This is often influenced by the inaccurate data collection process, both in terms of selecting potential beneficiaries and in maintaining recipient data. Despite efforts by village governments to verify and validate, errors in the data can cause ineligible recipients to remain recorded, while those who deserve assistance are missed.

2. Sosialisasi program bantuan langsung tunai dana desa untuk masyarakat miskin pada desa di Kecamatan Dungaliyo Kabupaten Gorontalo

The socialization of the Village Fund Direct Cash Assistance (BLT) program for the poor in villages in Dungaliyo District, Gorontalo Regency is an important step to ensure that all communities understand the objectives, mechanisms, as well as rights and obligations in participating in the program. This socialization process is carried out through various communication channels, such as village meetings, announcements through loudspeakers, social media, or distribution of information pamphlets. Involving community leaders and village institutions in socialization is the key so that information can be disseminated evenly and on target. Effective socialization ensures that no community is missed and minimizes the potential for misunderstandings or suspicions regarding transparency and fairness in aid distribution.

In the future, in order for socialization to be more effective, there needs to be a more inclusive and planned approach, such as increasing the frequency of meetings and using social media as a faster and more efficient information channel. In addition, the active role of the community in providing feedback is also important to increase understanding of this program. With a better

approach, people in Dungaliyo District will have an easier time understanding the mechanism and objectives of BLTDD, which can ultimately increase their participation in the program (Sutanto, 2022).

3. The purpose of the direct cash assistance program for village funds for the poor in villages in Dungaliyo District, Gorontalo Regency

The purpose of the Village Fund Direct Cash Assistance (BLT) program for the poor in villages in Dungaliyo District, Gorontalo Regency is to provide financial assistance that can be directly used to meet the basic needs of the underprivileged community. This program aims to ease the economic burden of the poor by providing funds that can be used to buy food, access to health, and education. In addition, another goal of BLT is to support the economic resilience of poor families, improve their living standards, and prevent them from falling deeper into extreme poverty. This program is also expected to improve social welfare at the village level by reducing the economic gap between residents.

However, to achieve these goals, BLTDD must be implemented with a careful approach, paying attention to transparency in distribution and avoiding abuse. Effective monitoring and strict supervision are also important factors to ensure that the aid actually reaches the people in need. If the objectives of BLTDD are carried out correctly, then this program can be one of the main instruments in improving the welfare of the poor in Dungaliyo District and in other villages in Gorontalo Regency (Ministry of Villages, Development of Disadvantaged Regions and Transmigration, 2021).

4. Monitoring of the village fund direct cash assistance program for the poor in villages in Dungaliyo District, Gorontalo Regency
- Monitoring the Village Fund Direct Cash Assistance (BLT) program for the poor in villages in Dungaliyo District, Gorontalo Regency is an activity carried out to ensure that the distribution of assistance runs in accordance with the established procedures and is on target. This monitoring process involves the village government, the Village Consultative Body (BPD), and the community, to evaluate the smooth distribution of aid and check whether the aid reaches the rightful. Monitoring also includes supervision of the use of funds received, whether they are used in accordance with the basic needs of beneficiaries. With effective monitoring, the BLT program can run more transparently, accountably, and minimize the potential for irregularities or misappropriations that can harm the poor.

To increase the effectiveness of monitoring, it is necessary to strengthen the capacity of village officials and the community in carrying out supervision. In addition, the use of information technology to monitor the distribution of aid in a more transparent manner can be one of the solutions. In this way, every BLTDD distribution process can be monitored in real-time, and the potential for misuse of funds can be minimized. Better monitoring not only increases public trust in the government, but also ensures that this program actually benefits the poor in Dungaliyo District (Amin, 2020).

This result is in accordance with the opinion of Agustina & Megawati (2022) that 1) Input, it can be said that it is optimal where the background for creating policies in accordance with the problems experienced by the community, then human resources, funds, and supporting infrastructure also greatly support the success of aid distribution. 2) The process, it can be said that it has not run optimally where the KPM is not aware of the existence of a social assistance check application to support the determination of the right KPM targets, then the aid distribution mechanism does not follow the applicable rules. 3) Outputs, which can be said to be optimal where the results of the policy can help the underprivileged meet their food needs, thus having an impact on the poverty level in. 4) Outcomes, it can be said that it has been optimal because the positive impact given by this BLT program is very wide.

The success of policy implementation can vary depending on the context, type of policy, and goals to be achieved. Wiwit, et al. (2020) said that the BLT program is expected to reduce the burden of expenditure in fulfilling the basic needs of poor families, as social protection and poverty alleviation. Successful implementation of policies such as BLT is often the result of a combination of factors and efforts that are integrated between communication, resources, implementing attitudes and bureaucratic structures. Therefore, good coordination between these factors is the key to achieving success in reducing poverty through direct cash assistance programs.

CONCLUSION

Based on the results of the research and discussion in the previous chapter, it can be concluded that the Village Fund Direct Cash Assistance Program (BLTDD) for the poor in Dungaliyo District, Gorontalo Regency has made a positive contribution in improving the welfare of people in need. The program has generally been running well although there is room for improvement, especially in target accuracy, socialization, and monitoring. A more holistic approach to implementation and evaluation can increase the

effectiveness of the program, resulting in a more equitable and sustainable positive impact on the poor. The results of each sub-focus are:

1. The accuracy of the target of the BLT Village Fund program in Dungaliyo District has been quite good with the efforts to improve recipient data carried out by the village government. While there are still challenges in reaching all poor families equally, the steps taken demonstrate a commitment to ensuring that assistance is received by those who really need it. Improving the data collection and verification process can improve the quality of distribution in the future.
2. The socialization of the Village Fund BLT program in Dungaliyo District has been carried out through various information channels, including the village government and related officials. However, the implementation needs to be more intensive so that the public better understands the objectives, benefits, and mechanisms of the program. With socialization that involves all elements of society, the effectiveness of information delivery can be improved, so that beneficiaries are more educated and the program runs more smoothly.
3. The main goal of the BLT Dana Desa program is to help poor families meet their basic needs and support the economic recovery of the village. In Dungaliyo District, this program has been quite effective in reducing the economic burden of the poor. By continuing to ensure the alignment of program goals and their implementation, the benefits felt by the community can be more optimal and sustainable.
4. Monitoring the implementation of the Village Fund BLT program in Dungaliyo District has been carried out routinely by the village government and related parties. This effort is quite effective in ensuring that assistance is received by those who are eligible. Going forward, increased transparency and data-driven evaluation can strengthen the monitoring system, so that the program can run more accountable and support continuous improvement

SUGGESTION

Based on the results of the research and the conclusions that have been described above, the suggestions of this research are as follows:

1. The Ministry of Villages, Development of Disadvantaged Regions and Transmigration of the Republic of Indonesia needs to strengthen technical guidelines and evaluation mechanisms for the implementation of the BLT Village Fund program. This includes the development of an integrated digital-based data collection system to ensure that recipient data is more accurate and up-to-date. In addition, training and assistance to village officials in running the program is also important to increase the effectiveness of aid distribution. The ministry is also advised to conduct periodic monitoring involving the community to ensure that the program runs according to its goals.
2. The Gorontalo Regency Community and Village Empowerment Office needs to strengthen coordination with the village government in compiling and updating data on aid recipients. In addition, the agency is expected to organize training to increase the capacity of village officials in the socialization, implementation, and monitoring of the BLT program. The provision of an effective complaint platform is also needed so that the public can submit complaints or input directly, so that the implementation of the program becomes more responsive and transparent.
3. The Dungaliyo District Government is expected to be more active in supervising the implementation of the Village Fund BLT in its area. This can be done through field visits and regular coordination meetings with the village government to monitor progress and overcome obstacles that arise. In addition, the sub-district needs to support the implementation of discussion forums between recipients, non-recipients, and the village government to create constructive and transparent communication related to this program.
4. The village government in Dungaliyo District is expected to continue to improve the quality of data collection for BLT recipients through careful verification and validation. Villages also need to expand the outreach of program socialization, involving all elements of society to ensure an equitable understanding. In addition, transparency in the distribution of aid through public announcements and periodic reports will help create public trust in the program.
5. Village supervisors need to carry out their supervisory functions more actively and independently. They are expected to monitor every stage of BLT implementation, starting from data collection to distribution. Supervision reports must be submitted transparently to the village and sub-district governments to become the basis for improvement. In addition, the supervisor is also advised to open a complaint room for the public to increase program accountability.

6. Community recipients of BLT Village Funds are expected to use the assistance wisely to meet the basic needs of their families. They also need to actively provide input or report inconsistencies in the implementation of the program to the authorities. In addition, recipients are expected to participate in evaluation activities or discussions held by the village government to increase the effectiveness of the program.
7. Non-BLT recipients are expected to continue to support the implementation of the program by maintaining a harmonious atmosphere and mutual respect in the village environment. They can also play an active role in providing constructive input related to data collection policies and the implementation of BLT. In addition, non-recipients are advised to take advantage of other empowerment programs provided by the government to improve their well-being independently.

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